

Indirect additive manufacturing of amphiphobic reentrant surface structures using fused deposition modelling

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ABSTRACT

Amphiphobic property, defined as repellency to liquids in general, can be achieved using reentrant structures with high edge angles. However, the complexity of forming an overhanging feature to create the reentrant feature with a high edge angle makes it challenging to manufacture using additive manufacturing technology. This study introduces a simple and cost-effective method for producing these structures, utilizing Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM) printed mold and silicone casting. The mold features a top layer with straight lines separated by gaps. A sharp acute angle is formed between a rounded filament and a relatively flat surface. This acute angle can be exploited to have the high edge angle of the desired reentrant structure upon replication with polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS). The best-performing reentrant surface structure obtained has an average edge angle of $\sim 120^\circ$ with additional surface topography on top of the structure due to material stacking during printing. It exhibited anisotropic wetting with an optimal water static contact angle of 160° and a minimal rolling angle of 29° for a $10 \mu\text{L}$ droplet. Furthermore, the structures also demonstrated superior repellency to ethylene glycol, a liquid with surface tension 35% lower than water. The achieved optimal static contact angle and minimal rolling angle for ethylene glycol are recorded as 163° and 14° , respectively. This study establishes the viability of a low-cost approach for attaining amphiphobicity in reentrant structures through an indirect FDM printer, presenting superior liquid-repelling properties to not just water but also to a lower surface tension liquid.

1. Introduction

Surface functionalization for repelling liquids can achieve properties such as anti-fouling (Reddy et al., 2011) and self-cleaning (El-Atab et al., 2020), to name a few. The introduction of structure to a surface causes a change in surface energy, which in turn modifies how the surface interacts with contacting liquid. This causes conditions such as enhancing the surfaces' liquid-repelling properties. Drawing inspiration from natural surface topographies is paramount for designing liquid-repelling surfaces, with examples like the hierarchical micro/nanostructures of lotus leaves and the reentrant overhanging structures on springtail cuticles (Li et al., 2023). While various structures have been developed to mimic this functionality, such designs commonly adopt the form of either pillars or reentrant structures. Notably, reentrant structures resembling the shape of a mushroom prove to be the most effective and can repel not just water but also low-surface tension liquids such as oil (Li et al., 2023). Their efficacy correlates with the large angle of the overhanging feature or the edge angle of the structure (φ). A larger edge angle enhances liquid repellency by directing the net force outward of

the structure, preventing liquid flow toward the bottom of the structure's cavity (Li et al., 2023).

Additive manufacturing is a highly attractive process to create reentrant structures due to its versatility and fast production capable of producing complex shapes. Given this technology's promise, numerous studies have been undertaken to produce biomimetic structures. Achieving surface textures that mimic the micro and nanoscale (Li et al., 2023) characteristics seen in nature depends critically on the 3D printer's resolution. Among the commercially available options, the Two-Photon Polymerization (TPP) printer stands out for having the highest resolution (Wang et al., 2023). While successful studies utilizing TPP printers to produce reentrant structures exist (Dong and Levkin, 2023), its widespread industrial application is impeded by factors such as high cost, limited build envelope, and long printing times. Due to these, other additive manufacturing technologies are still being explored.

One convenient way of getting superior water repellency is to have hierarchical micro-nano structures, where the microstructures are 3D printed and the nanoroughness is introduced by incorporating nano-

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Fig. 1. Schematic of preparation of the mold. (a) A 3D model of the mold with a flat surface was drawn using CAD software. (b) The G-code program for printing the model was made in slicing software with a defined infill line distance to have a gap in between the printed lines. (c) The G-code is then transferred to an FDM unit for printing the final product having visible printed lines.

Table 1
Parameters set in the slicing software.

Slicing Parameter	Set Values
Layer height	0.1 mm
Printing temperature	200 °C
Build plate temperature	50 °C
Flow	95
Infill speed	20 mm/s
Infill line pattern	Lines
Infill line distance	See Table 2

sized particles like nanosilica into the resin/ ink. This approach applies to technologies such as Digital Light Processing (DLP) (Kaur et al., 2020), Direct Ink Writing (DIW) (Lv et al., 2017), and Material Jetting (Chand et al., 2023). Alternatively, nanoparticle coatings can be applied to the surfaces of FDM-printed parts (Lee et al., 2019). These

nanoparticles, however, may impose toxicity on the human body (Huang et al., 2022). The achievement of liquid-repelling surfaces necessitates the consideration of materials with low surface energy (Shams et al., 2021). Hence, fluorine-based coatings on 3D printed parts (Shams et al., 2021) can also be an alternative but these are found to have a negative impact on human health and the environment (Cirisano and Ferrari, 2021).

Silicone, an environmentally friendly material recognized among polymers for its exceptionally low surface energy next to fluoropolymers, can be a viable option for achieving superior liquid-repelling properties (Bunea et al., 2023). However, direct additive manufacturing of PDMS with reentrant structures having high edge angles is challenging using Digital Light Processing (DLP) because there is currently no commercial PDMS-based resin with high-resolution (<100 μm features) capability unless photoabsorbers are added to the resin (Fleck et al., 2021). If the edge angle is not kept to as big as possible, it can lead to adhesion of the liquid to the structure without

Fig. 2. Schematic showing the fabrication process of the PDMS cast. (a) PDMS was prepared and poured into the FDM-printed mold. (b) The PDMS with the mold is then transferred into a vacuum chamber and degassed until all bubbles are removed. (c) After degassing, PDMS is cured in an oven at 40 °C for 20 hrs. (d) The cured PDMS is detached from the mold. (e) Formed PDMS with a zoom-in view showing the reentrant structure.

Fig. 3. Arranged from left to right are the optical cross-sectional images of 1- and 2-layer structures, laser microscope surface profiles of 1-layer structures in a 1.28×1.28 mm area, and the surface profiles on top of the reentrant structures. These were taken on the PDMS cast from molds printed using different nozzle sizes: 0.2 mm (does not have 2-layer structure), 0.3 mm, 0.4 mm, 0.5 mm, and 0.6 mm.

exhibiting droplet rolling as was achieved by Yin et al. (2021) who used DLP. Moreover, photoresins are expensive and the number of commercially available PDMS-based resins is limited (Herzberger et al., 2019). TPP can be another option and was used by Bunea et al. (2023) to directly 3D print superhydrophobic reentrant structures using commercially available PDMS resin suited for this type of printer. However, this method has drawbacks as previously mentioned. Another

method of 3D printing is indirect printing wherein a mold is printed from which the structure can be replicated. If indirect additive manufacturing is pursued using DLP, the large curing depth of commercial resins would prevent it from having a mold with a thin or sharp undercut except if a special resin is custom formulated with photo-absorbers or a special setup is employed (Xu et al., 2022). Another option is to use FDM printing.

Table 2

Different printing parameters set and the average measurements, with corresponding 1 standard deviation, of the resulting PDMS reentrant structures.

Nozzle Dia. [mm]	Infill Line Distance [mm]	No. of layers [-]	Top width (<i>w</i>) [μm]	Top spacing (<i>s</i>) [μm]	Height (<i>h</i>) [μm]	Edge angle (<i>φ</i>) [°]	Roughness on the structure's top surface		
							Sq [μm]	Str [-]	Std [°]
0.2	0.275	1	119 ± 12	153 ± 11	87 ± 4	119 ± 14	0.7 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.1	88 ± 3
0.2	0.3	1	147 ± 8	150 ± 10	87 ± 9	116 ± 15	0.9 ± 0.4	0.1 ± 0.1	90 ± 3
0.3	0.375	1	140 ± 23	236 ± 11	96 ± 5	123 ± 8	0.4 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.2	90 ± 2
0.3	0.4	1	173 ± 22	224 ± 12	96 ± 3	121 ± 9	0.4 ± 0.2	0.2 ± 0.1	89 ± 2
0.3	0.4	2	160 ± 20	232 ± 12	205 ± 4	118 ± 9	0.4 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.1	91 ± 2
0.4	0.475	1	144 ± 27	328 ± 15	101 ± 2	126 ± 5	0.5 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.1	91 ± 1
0.4	0.5	1	163 ± 30	335 ± 25	96 ± 4	125 ± 6	0.5 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.1	91 ± 3
0.4	0.5	2	172 ± 25	325 ± 16	207 ± 4	124 ± 6	0.5 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.1	91 ± 2
0.5	0.6	1	157 ± 28	440 ± 21	95 ± 3	125 ± 12	0.5 ± 0.2	0.9 ± 0.04	65 ± 7
0.5	0.6	2	150 ± 29	446 ± 17	197 ± 5	121 ± 10	0.5 ± 0.2	0.8 ± 0.1	62 ± 13
0.6	0.7	1	161 ± 27	535 ± 21	96 ± 2	123 ± 7	0.5 ± 0.1	0.8 ± 0.1	66 ± 9
0.6	0.7	2	147 ± 30	544 ± 24	206 ± 2	121 ± 8	0.5 ± 0.1	0.7 ± 0.2	73 ± 10

There are emerging studies in the pursuit of creating low-cost liquid-repellent structures using FDM (Shams et al., 2021). Indirect FDM 3D printing was done by Kang et al. (2020) by printing molds with a surface comprised of several inverted pyramidal shapes with a 50° vertex angle. The resulting cast PDMS has surface structures with a pyramidal shape with ridges around it which is due to the stair-case effect of FDM printing. It achieved a hydrophobic surface with a water contact angle of ~143° and water droplet rolling at 50°. Han et al. (2021) utilized this concept and printed a mold in an inclined position. They were able to obtain a lower roll-off angle of up to 5° on this structure by etching the printed mold with a solvent to create a rougher surface. This method of printing the mold in an inclined position was further optimized in a separate study by Kang et al. (2021) by varying the mold tilting angle. The resulting surface structures in the form of ridges with sharp top tips achieved a superhydrophobic surface with a water contact angle of 160° and a rolling angle of 8°. This was optimally obtained at a mold printing angle of 70°. This is primarily due to the sharp top tip of the ridge and a high aspect ratio of structure height versus pitch distance. A study by Park et al. (2022) showed that when the overall design is added with holes, it can be applied for water-oil separation proving its repellence to water but not to low surface tension liquids. To repel lower surface tension liquids, reentrant structures should be considered. The first and only study to date to explore forming reentrant structures using FDM was done in a preliminary investigation by Shams et al. (2021). A one-step process of direct 3D printing was done to produce channels and utilized the stair-case effect of FDM-printed part to form the reentrant structure. The reentrant feature here, having rounded edges, obtained a water static contact angle of 129°. Moreover, they consider it to be amphiphobic as it can obtain a high static contact angle of 117° to glycerol, which has a slightly lower surface tension ($\gamma = 63.7$ mN/m) compared to water ($\gamma = 72.9$ mN/m) (Oosterlaken and De With, 2022). It is possible that there was no liquid roll-off on these surfaces as no data was presented on this. The rounded edge of the reentrant feature has a low edge angle that promotes wetting on that part of the structure. At such an angle, the hydrophilic property of the polylactic acid (PLA) filament used also significantly affects it. The combination of a low reentrant edge angle and the hydrophilic material used explains the relatively low static contact angle obtained with no demonstration of

liquid roll-off. The study we present here explores improving this by using an inherently hydrophobic silicone material and forming reentrant structures with sharp edges that in turn make it have a high edge angle. This can be done using indirect FDM printing.

In this study, we created amphiphobic reentrant structures with sharp edges on a PDMS which was cast from a mold printed using FDM. A gap is made between the printed lines. There is a sharp acute angle between a rounded filament and a relatively flat surface. This acute angle on the mold caused the high edge angle of the desired reentrant structure when cast with PDMS. The obtained reentrant structure is in the form of a continuous wall having an additional surface topography on top of the reentrant structure. The amphiphobic property was optimized by controlling the reentrant structures' width, height, and spacing in between structures. The unique structures inherent to the FDM process were first characterized by their static and dynamic behavior with water. Static contact angles were compared with theoretical predictions. The best three performing samples demonstrating hydrophobic properties were then further tested using a lower surface tension ethylene glycol ($\gamma = 47.4$ mN/m). These structures proved to exhibit an amphiphobic property having a superior static contact angle greater than 150° to not just water but also to ethylene glycol and demonstrating droplet roll-off to both liquids. The ethylene glycol used here is of much lower surface tension than the glycerol ($\gamma = 63.7$ mN/m) used in the study by Shams et al. (2021) previously mentioned. Thus, the proposed method here improves the current state-of-the-art amphiphobic properties of reentrant surface structures that can be obtained using a low-cost FDM additive manufacturing technology. The analogy of the method used here can serve as inspiration for other avenues of producing cost-effective amphiphobic surfaces.

2. Experimental methods

2.1. Preparation of FDM-printed mold

The mold for FDM printing was drawn using SolidWorks 2021 Computer-Aided Design (CAD) software. The 3D model as shown in Fig. 1a does not involve drawing intricate features on the part. The surface structures on the mold were later introduced by setting up the

Fig. 4. (a) Schematic of measuring static contact angles in different views: (b) front and (c) side views. Measurements in (b) and (c) were the average obtained for 3 replicates with corresponding 1 standard deviation. Different static contact angles are measured on the front view in almost the same location but slightly offset to drop the liquid (d) directly on top of the wall or (e) in between the walls. Measurements in (d) and (e) show an average and 1 standard deviation of 5 repeated measurements in 1 sample.

slicing parameters in Ultimaker Cura 5.1.0 slicing software.

The slicing process involved digitally transforming the design into a G-code toolpath for the printer's extruder to follow to form the 3D part. The top surface of the mold was sliced in such a way that there is a gap between extruded filaments as shown in Fig. 1b. This was done in the software by using the "Infill Line Distance" which is defined as the distance between the center of the two adjacent printed lines. This gap between infill lines will form the column of the reentrant structure. By controlling the infill line distance, the width of the reentrant structure can be varied. The layer below the topmost layer was sliced using the "Support Blocker Distance" function with the same infill line distance as the topmost layer but with an offset equivalent to half of the infill line distance. This was done to create an alternating layer of infill lines. The walls to contain the PDMS were designed not to cover the whole base area as seen in Fig. 1a to avoid replicating the wavy side of the extruded lines brought by the jerking motion of the extruder during the sudden change of toolpath direction.

The mold was printed using a Prusa MK3S+ (Prusa Research A.S., Czech Republic) FDM printer with PrimaValue white PLA filament (PrimaCreator, Sweden). Different nozzle sizes were used in this study: 0.4 mm (Prusa Research A.S., Czech Republic) and 0.2, 0.3, 0.5 and 0.6 mm (E3D for V5 and V6 hotends, Techbitsshop, Denmark). By changing the nozzle sizes, different spacing distances can be made

between reentrant structures. Moreover, height was also varied from one to two layers by adding an infill line layer directly on top of another.

In summary, the optimal amphiphobic property was obtained in this study by using the infill line distance, nozzle size, and number of layers as variables to adjust the reentrant structure's width, spacing, and height, respectively. The parameters set in the slicer are detailed in Table 1. These were the chosen set of parameters as these can accommodate printing using the wide range of nozzle sizes used with no demonstration of the merging of infill lines.

2.2. Casting of PDMS

The PDMS was cast in the mold after printing in FDM. The schematic of the casting process is shown in Fig. 2. PDMS (Sylgard 184, Dow Corning Inc.) was prepared by mixing prepolymer and curing agent at a 10:1 ratio. This was poured into the 3D-printed mold and then degassed in a desiccator with a connection to a vacuum line. It was done until no visible bubbles were found. This was followed by curing in an oven set at 40 °C for 20 hrs. After this, the PDMS cast was detached from the mold.

2.3. Static and dynamic contact angle measurements

To verify the amphiphobic properties of the obtained surface structures, the samples were tested with different liquids having different surface tensions. In this study, deionized (DI) water and ethylene glycol (Fluka Analytical, Sigma Aldrich) were used. The ethylene glycol used here has a surface tension of 47.36 ± 0.02 mN/m as characterized using an optical tensiometer (Attension Theta Lite, Biolin Scientific, Sweden). The static contact angles of 10 μ L liquid droplets were measured using a contact angle goniometer (Ramé-Hart Instrument Co., USA). Three samples were produced per set of parameters and the static contact angles were measured five times in random locations across the surface. The samples were also tested with much lower surface tension liquids such as olive oil ($\gamma = 32$ mN/m) and isopropanol ($\gamma = 23$ mN/m) but were found to completely wet the surface. Hence, these were not included in this study.

The rolling angles and dynamic contact angles were measured five times per sample using the tilting method. This was done by dropping 10 μ L DI water on the surface of the structured PDMS which was placed on a tiltable platform. This platform was rotated slowly until the droplet rolled off completely across the surface. This entire process was viewed using the contact angle goniometer software (DROPimage v2.4.07) and recorded in screen-recording software (Free Cam v8). A snapshot of the time at which the droplet rolled off was taken and analyzed in an image processing program (ImageJ v1.47) wherein the roll-off angles and dynamic contact angles were measured.

2.4. Visual inspection and surface roughness analysis

Surface profiles of ten wall structures and ten spacings per sample were taken to measure the top surface width (w), spacing between the structures (s), and height of the structures (h). This was done using Olympus LEXT Infinite Laser Microscope and analyzed using surface analysis software (MountainsMap v9.3). Inspections were done using a 20x lens for the structures replicated from molds printed using a 0.2 mm nozzle and a 10x lens for the 0.3-, 0.4-, 0.5-, and 0.6-mm nozzle sizes.

The surface profiles to measure the local surface roughness at the top of the reentrant structures were all taken using a 50x lens in the same laser microscope. Six surface profiles were obtained per sample. An area of 100×250 μ m was first extracted from the surface profile and then least squares plane leveling was applied. In cases where the structure's top width is smaller than 100 μ m, the extracted area is set to the maximum width possible. A second-order polynomial degree was used to remove the form. The surface roughness parameters, specifically the root mean square height (S_q), texture aspect ratio (Str), and texture direction (Std), were measured using the MountainsMap software as per

Fig. 5. Characterized static and dynamic behavior of water plotted against spacing-to-width ratio (s/w). Static contact angles taken in (a) front and (b) side views. Rolling angles when the sample is tilted for the water droplet to roll (c) perpendicular to the reentrant wall pattern and (d) parallel to it. (e) Dynamic contact angles on both rolling directions. Error bars indicate 1 standard deviation obtained from 15 measurements.

Fig. 6. Complete wetting of water droplet on PDMS surface cast from mold printed using 0.6 mm nozzle.

ISO 25178. Str was obtained using an autocorrelation threshold of 0.8 to be able to calculate it on all surface profiles without the autocorrelation lobe touching the edges.

Colored images of the cross-section of the structure were taken using an optical microscope (Carl Zeiss A/S) with AxioCam ICc 5 camera. High-contrast cross-section images were taken using the Keyence VHX-6000 microscope from which the edge angles of the reentrant features were measured using ImageJ. Ten measurements per sample were done for this.

3. Results and discussion

The cross-sections of the resulting surface structures with different parameters on PDMS are shown in Fig. 3 with the actual dimensions of the features detailed in Table 2. The bigger nozzle size gave a higher spacing because of the larger amount of extruded material. Given the same nozzle size, using a smaller infill line distance means a smaller gap between two printed lines in the mold and therefore results in a smaller reentrant structure width. The height was varied by stacking printed lines on top of each other. The average edge angle of the structures in all samples was measured to be around $121.8^\circ \pm 10.0^\circ$. A mold with 2 layers using the 0.2 mm nozzle was not included due to the observed damage of structures during demolding. This can be caused by the small infill line distance that made the printed lines merge with each other.

Based on Table 2, which details the local surface roughness analysis on the top of the reentrant structure, the Sq ranges from 0.5 to 0.9 μm . The structures replicated from molds printed using 0.2-, 0.3-, and 0.4-mm nozzles have Str values near 0, indicating a strong anisotropy in the texture direction (Std) close to 90° which is the printing direction of the nozzle. Reentrant structures from molds produced with 0.5- and 0.6-mm nozzles, on the other hand, have Str values close to 1, implying significant isotropy. This large difference in surface topography can be seen in Fig. 3. The change in surface topography from small to bigger nozzle sizes can be attributed to the stacking of more deposited material (Wang et al., 2019) with a larger nozzle size.

3.1. Anisotropic wetting and the effect of drop placement location

The wall structure resulted in a different wetting behavior as seen in the different views of the sample (Fig. 4a). There is an observed higher water static contact angle as seen on the front view (Fig. 4b) as compared to the side view (Fig. 4c). The high static contact angle measured in the front view is caused by the sharp edges that act as energy barriers and create constraint force (Liu et al., 2022) impeding the spread of water. On the side view, however, the water spreads freely on the continuous surface of the wall thus giving a lower static contact angle (Nagato et al., 2019).

Two distinct static contact angles were obtained during the contact angle measurements based on the droplet placement. The droplet placement could be in between the wall structure or in line with the wall structure. This resulted in a different wetting behavior of the droplet as it could cover different areas according to what the size of the droplet can

cover based on where it is placed. It could cover 5 walls (Fig. 4d) that can give a higher static contact angle of 155° or 6 walls (Fig. 4e) that exhibit a lower static contact angle of 139° . In the following sections, the droplets that are placed such that they give a higher static contact angle would be termed “High Static Contact Angle” (HSCA) droplets, and the lower to be “Low Static Contact Angle” (LSCA) droplets.

3.2. Wetting properties characterized using water

The measured static contact angles (θ) can be compared to the theoretical values as modeled by Cassie-Baxter and Wenzel’s theories. The apparent contact angle in the complete wetting as defined by Wenzel’s theory is given by:

$$\cos\theta_w = r\cos\theta_Y \quad (1)$$

where θ_Y is Young’s contact angle which is the contact angle of the liquid on a flat surface of the material, and r is the roughness factor which is the ratio between the real and project surface area. The measured static contact angle for a flat surface in the PDMS is $114^\circ \pm 3^\circ$ and is used for calculating the theoretical contact angles. The reentrant structures obtained in this study have r that can be defined as:

$$r = 1 + \frac{2a}{w(1+s/w)} \quad (2)$$

for 1-layer structure, and:

$$r = 1 + \frac{4a}{w(1+s/w)} \quad (3)$$

for a 2-layer structure, where a is the arc length of the sides of the wall structure for a 1-layer height. This arc length can be obtained based on the edge angle and the height of the structures with the assumption that the side walls are in the form of a circular arc to simplify the calculations.

Cassie-Baxter theory, on the other hand, models the liquid to be completely lifted by the surface structures. The apparent contact angle based on this theory is expressed as:

$$\cos\theta_{CB} = f\cos\theta_Y + f - 1 \quad (4)$$

where f is the surface fraction defined as the ratio of the area contacting the droplet in the structured surface to the projected area. In the structures obtained here, this can be defined as:

$$f = \frac{1}{1+s/w} \quad (5)$$

In Fig. 5a,b, the theoretical contact angles defined by Wenzel’s and Cassie-Baxter’s models as expressed in Eqs. (1) and (4), respectively, were plotted against the ratio of the spacing (s) between the structures and the width (w) of the top of the reentrant structures for comparison with the actual contact angles. In theory, the droplets should follow Wenzel’s theory on s/w from 0.8 and onwards since this is the lower energy state in these structures’ features and therefore the more stable state. However, it can be observed that the LSCA values taken in the front view for 0.2–0.5 mm nozzles follow the Cassie-Baxter curve and the HSCA values at all nozzle sizes were high above the predicted Cassie-Baxter contact angles. These were reaching above 150° , a condition where the surface can be termed superhydrophobic. The high static contact angles for the cast from molds printed using nozzles sized 0.2–0.4 mm are due to the overhanging structure effectively keeping the water droplet on top of its structure. At 0.5 mm, 1-layer structure, there are cases where the droplet starts to wet until the bottom of the structure. Not all instances though were observed to be fully wetting, thus giving a large standard deviation of the static contact angles. This is the point where the metastable Cassie-Baxter state can no longer be maintained, and the system starts to go to the more stable Wenzel state. Using

Fig. 7. Static and dynamic behavior of water and ethylene glycol of the three best-performing samples in terms of hydrophobicity as discussed in the previous section. Static contact angle in the front (a) and side (b) view of the samples. Rolling angle and dynamic contact angles (advancing and receding) for a droplet rolling perpendicular (c) to the wall pattern and parallel to it (d). The sample from the 0.6 mm nozzle is not included in the dynamic behavior characterization due to the apparent liquid intrusion observed during the static contact angle measurements using ethylene glycol. Error bars indicate 1 standard deviation obtained from 15 measurements.

a 0.6 mm nozzle, the structure with one layer demonstrated wetting of water to the bottom, hence causing a drop of the static contact angle. Taking a closer look at the wetting on this structure as shown in Fig. 6, the water did not completely wet the sides of the wall indicating effective pinning of the liquid at the edges of the reentrant structure. The intrusion of the liquid in the 1-layer structure using 0.5- and 0.6-mm nozzles was due to the large spacing and low height. This resulted in less support for the droplet and a low volume of entrapped air to keep the droplet from sagging to the bottom. Adding more volume of entrapped air beneath the droplet was done by increasing the overall height of the structure through the addition of a layer on top. At the 2-layer height, the structures from 0.5- and 0.6-mm nozzles transitioned

from the wetting state to the Cassie-Baxter state with optimal static contact angles of $160^\circ \pm 3^\circ$ and $157^\circ \pm 3^\circ$, respectively.

The effect of increasing the overall structures' height can be clearly seen on contact angles obtained on the side view (Fig. 5b). From 0.2–0.4 mm nozzles, the side contact angles were slightly lower than the Cassie-Baxter curve but still followed its general trend of increasing contact angle as s/w increases. At 0.5 mm nozzle, the contact angle of the 1-layer structure starts to drop due to the wetting as previously mentioned. At 2-layer heights of 0.5- and 0.6-mm nozzles, the contact angles maintain to be high following the Cassie-Baxter trend.

It should be noted that Eqs. (2), (3), and (5) to express r and f do not consider the local surface roughness obtained on the top of the reentrant

Fig. 8. Static contact angle as seen on the front view of (a) water and (b) ethylene glycol on the same sample, which is printed from 0.5 mm nozzle, 0.6 mm infill line distance, and 2 no. of layers.

structures due to the complexity of incorporating the stochastic surface texture into the equations. Moreover, the effect of different surface topography obtained from small (0.2, 0.3, 0.4 mm) and large (0.5, 0.6 mm) nozzles cannot be directly determined due to the difficulty of controlling the top surface topography while keeping all other factors constant (e.g. reentrant structures' width, height, edge angle, spacing). The use of larger nozzle sizes comes with the accompanying increase of the spacing. In theory, though, as plotted in Fig. 5a,b, adding surface roughness can only result in having static contact angles equal to or higher than Young's contact angle. Therefore, it is possible that the local surface roughness at the top of the structure contributed to the higher static contact angles compared to when it is completely smooth.

The measured rolling angles are plotted against s/w in Fig. 5c,d for rolling of the droplet perpendicular and parallel to the wall structure, respectively. The plot in Fig. 5c does not distinguish between HSCA and LSCA droplets because it was observed that the LSCA droplet slightly moves first to form an equivalent HSCA droplet before it completely rolls off (as seen on the image on the top left of the graph). The opposite (LSCA forming to HSCA) was also observed. Both Fig. 5c,d show that the increase in the nozzle size for 2-layer structures results in a decreasing rolling angle at the direction perpendicular and parallel to the wall. This is due to the decrease in length of the three-phase contact line (TCL) with a decreasing wall's top surface area. A shorter TCL contributes to lesser adhesion and spreading of the liquid (Liu et al., 2018). The same trend can also be seen for 1-layer height but only until 0.4 mm nozzle. At 0.5- and 0.6-mm nozzle, no rolling was observed due to the droplet's adhesion to the structure when the liquid fully intruded towards the bottom of the structure.

When comparing Fig. 5c,d, it is evident that the rolling angle is greater when the droplet is rolled in a perpendicular direction to the wall, in contrast to when it is rolled parallel to the wall. This difference in rolling angle can be attributed to the liquid becoming pinned at the edges of the reentrant structures when rolled perpendicular to them. In contrast, when rolled parallel to the structures, the liquid flows smoothly along a continuous surface without encountering any edges. The 2-layered structures from molds printed using 0.5- and 0.6-mm nozzle gave the lowest rolling angle of $29^\circ \pm 4^\circ$ and $30^\circ \pm 4^\circ$, respectively, at the rolling direction parallel to the wall structures.

In Fig. 5c,d, HSCA droplets are observed to have lower rolling angles than their respective LSCA droplets in the rolling direction parallel to the wall. This can be explained by the shorter TCL length in HSCA droplets compared to the LSCA droplets.

The advancing and receding contact angles of droplets showing roll-off are detailed in Fig. 5e. The contact angle hysteresis (CAH), defined as the difference between the advancing and receding contact angle can be viewed in the graphs as the gap between these two plotted angles. In theory, a high contact angle hysteresis implies a high roll-off angle and vice versa (Shams et al., 2021). It can be observed that the gap between the advancing and receding angle is higher in droplets rolled

perpendicular to the wall pattern compared to the parallel direction. This affirms the rolling angle data in Fig. 5c,d that show a higher rolling-off angle in the direction perpendicular to the wall pattern compared to the parallel direction.

3.3. Wetting properties characterized using ethylene glycol

The three sets of samples showing the highest water-repelling behavior as analyzed from the previous section were then tested with ethylene glycol which has a static contact angle of $97 \pm 1^\circ$ on a flat PDMS surface. The static contact angles of ethylene glycol on the reentrant structures are shown in Fig. 7a,b which also include a comparison with the data obtained using water. In the front view (Fig. 7a), the static contact angles for HSCA ethylene glycol droplets in all the samples are greater than 150° and greater than the Cassie-Baxter theoretical prediction. The samples from 0.4-, 0.5-, and 0.6-mm nozzles obtained a front static contact angle of $161 \pm 2^\circ$, $163 \pm 3^\circ$, and $164 \pm 3^\circ$, respectively for an HSCA ethylene glycol droplet. However, the samples printed using the 0.6 mm nozzle started to show liquid intrusion up to the bottom of the structure. The spacing between the structures in this sample is already reaching its maximum limit on keeping the liquid in a Cassie-Baxter state. Still, the reentrant structures from nozzles 0.4 and 0.5 mm prove their ability to create a stable Cassie-Baxter state up to a liquid with a surface tension of 47.4 mN/m. Additionally, these static contact angles in the front view obtained for ethylene glycol are higher compared to water. A closer look to compare how the two liquids behave on the sample printed from a 0.5 mm nozzle can be seen in Fig. 8. Ethylene glycol droplets, having a lower surface tension than water, tend to sag downwards thereby causing a higher measured static contact angle. Conversely, when viewed from the side view, ethylene glycol exhibits a lower static contact angle than water (Fig. 7b). This can still be attributed to the lower surface tension of ethylene glycol that facilitates its enhanced spreading behavior.

The data on the dynamic behavior of the two liquids are shown in Fig. 7c,d with liquid rolling perpendicular and parallel directions to the wall pattern, respectively. The samples printed from the 0.6 mm nozzle are no longer measured here due to the apparent intrusion of ethylene glycol into the structures. With the same observation as water, the ethylene glycol droplets also showed a higher rolling angle in the rolling direction perpendicular to the wall pattern compared to parallel to it. The samples printed using 0.4- and 0.5-mm nozzles demonstrated rolling angles of $32 \pm 5^\circ$ and $32 \pm 7^\circ$, respectively when the ethylene glycol droplet is rolled in the perpendicular direction to the wall pattern. The liquid droplet rolling on a sample from the 0.5 mm nozzle can be seen in Fig. 9 with its real-time video in Movie S1. When rolling in a perpendicular direction, a small amount of liquid remains on top of the structures in both liquids implying a high energy barrier effectively pinning the liquid in these edges during the rolling test.

On the rolling direction parallel to the wall pattern, the HSCA ethylene glycol droplets showed rolling angles of $16 \pm 2^\circ$ and $14 \pm 4^\circ$ for samples printed using 0.4- and 0.5-mm nozzles, respectively. In both rolling directions, ethylene glycol exhibits significantly lower rolling angles than water. This can be explained by the Furmidge equation (Furmidge, 1962) for predicting the rolling angle, α :

$$\rho g V \sin \alpha = \gamma w (\cos \theta_R - \cos \theta_A) \quad (6)$$

where ρ is the liquid density, g is the gravity acceleration, V is the liquid volume, γ is the liquid surface tension, w is the width of the droplet, θ_R is the receding contact angle, and θ_A is the advancing contact angle. Among these factors, the relatively large difference between the two liquids' surface tension can justify why the lower surface tension ethylene glycol demonstrated a lower rolling angle compared to water.

Fig. 9. Sequence of images of (a) water and (b) ethylene glycol droplets rolling parallel and perpendicular to the 2-layer structure wall replicated from mold printed from 0.5 mm nozzle. The arrows emphasize small traces of liquid left after complete droplet roll-off in the perpendicular direction.

4. Conclusion

In this study, we have developed an amphiphobic surface by forming reentrant structures with sharp edges on a PDMS substrate, which was derived from a mold made via FDM printing. The distinct acute angle formed between the printed filament and the relatively flat surface led to the development of sharp-edged reentrant structures during the replication process with PDMS. This resulted in the formation of a continuous reentrant wall pattern displaying an anisotropic wetting behavior towards both water and ethylene glycol. Notably, the static contact angle

observed from the front view, where the reentrant structures are visible, was higher than that from the side view. Both liquids demonstrated roll-off when the sample was tilted. The rolling angle was lower when rolled parallel to the wall structure compared to perpendicular to it.

The most favorable outcomes were obtained with a two-layered reentrant structure produced from a mold printed using a 0.5 mm nozzle, which exhibited an additional surface roughness atop its structure due to material stacking resulting from the relatively large nozzle size. This sample attained water static contact angles of $160^\circ \pm 3^\circ$ and $127^\circ \pm 3^\circ$ from the front and side views, respectively, for a 10 μL water

droplet. Similarly, it demonstrated superior static contact angles using ethylene glycol, reaching $163 \pm 3^\circ$ and $120 \pm 4^\circ$ from the front and side views, respectively. Additionally, it displayed low rolling angles of $29^\circ \pm 4^\circ$ and $14 \pm 4^\circ$ for water and ethylene glycol, respectively, when rolled parallel to the wall pattern direction. These attained properties were found to surpass the current state-of-the-art amphiphobic surfaces achievable using FDM printing (Shams et al., 2021).

This study can be further improved by examining the effect of added surface roughness on top of the reentrant structures through printing parameter optimization. Moreover, future investigations could explore the reproducibility of casting structures using the same mold, an aspect not explored in this study due to the difficulty of inspecting undercut regions. Additionally, the concept of strategically arranging filaments with gaps between them extends beyond FDM and can be implemented using alternative methods. Employing a more precise manufacturing method to create molds with such rounded filaments could potentially yield improved results. Still, the characterization of the liquid behavior on the distinctive surface morphology achieved in this study through the FDM printing process could enhance the understanding of wetting phenomena, thereby facilitating improved liquid manipulation in future applications.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Myka Mae Duran: Writing – original draft, Writing - review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Yang Zhang:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Aminul Islam:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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